

Coon and Tucker “*Measuring motivation for forage in feedlot cattle fed a high-concentrate diet using a short-term thwarting test*”

Supplemental Figure 1. Plastic bin (12.7 x 50.8 x 38.1 cm) containing beardless wheat hay positioned in feed bunk. Nine white lines were spray painted approximately 10 cm apart on the lip of the feed bunk to denote the position of the bin and to facilitate recording its movements. Sixteen finishing animals were offered 1 of 2 treatments in the plastic bins: 1) TMR: 200 g of a total mixed ration (18% roughage; n=9) or 2) WH: 200 g of beardless wheat hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=7).

Coon and Tucker “*Measuring motivation for forage in feedlot cattle fed a high-concentrate diet using a short-term thwarting test*”

Supplemental Figure 2. Beardless wheat hay in a plastic bin (12.7 x 50.8 x 38.1 cm) with a wire mesh covering secured with zip ties to thwart animals' access to the contents. Sixteen finishing animals were offered 1 of 2 treatments in the plastic bins: 1) TMR: 200 g of a total mixed ration (18% roughage; n=9) or 2) WH: 200 g of beardless wheat hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=7).

Coon and Tucker "Measuring motivation for forage in feedlot cattle fed a high-concentrate diet using a short-term thwarting test"

Supplemental Table S1. Effect of eight short-term exposures to 100 g of either TMR* or WH* on behaviours in beef cattle analyzed as a percentage of total time with the treatment

Variable	ANOVA (Type II SS)								
	DF*	Treatment		DF**	Exposure		DF**	Interaction	
		chisq	p-value		chisq	p-value		chisq	p-value
Latency (%)	1	0.89	0.35	1	0.07	0.79	1	0.40	0.53
Head in bin (%)	1	0.03	0.85	1	22.07	<0.01	1	1.05	0.30
Head near bin (%)	1	0.04	0.84	1	3.70	0.05	1	0.94	0.33

*TMR: 100 g of a total mixed ration (18% roughage; n=9) and WH: 100 g of beardless wheat hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=7)

**Numerator DF obtained from the ANOVA type II SS are presented; denominator DF are known to be erroneous in many mixed models and are not presented (e.g. <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>)

Supplemental Table S2. Back-transformed means and SE for models analyzing the effect of eight short-term exposures to 100 g of either TMR* or WH* on behaviours (mean ± SE) in beef cattle analyzed as a percentage of total time with the treatment

Variable	Treatment							
	WH				TMR			
	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit
Latency (%)	7.34	1.56	4.79	11.10	8.91	1.58	6.24	11.26
Head in bin (%)	6.17	1.42	3.89	9.64	5.96	1.21	3.96	8.87
Head near bin (%)	3.20	0.67	2.11	4.82	3.00	0.67	2.06	4.35

*TMR: 100 g of a total mixed ration (18% roughage; n=9) and WH: 100 g of beardless wheat hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=7)

Coon and Tucker “*Measuring motivation for forage in feedlot cattle fed a high-concentrate diet using a short-term thwarting test*”

Supplemental Table S3. Effect of eight short-term exposures to 100 g of either TMR* or WH* on behaviours in beef cattle analyzed as a rate

Variable	ANOVA (Type III SS)								
	DF	Treatment		DF	Exposure		DF	Interaction	
		chisq	p-value		chisq	p-value		chisq	p-value
Bin movements (#/min)	14	6.20	0.01	101	18.25	<0.01	101	11.65	<0.01
Intake (g/min)	14	10.88	<0.01	101	56.17	<0.01	101	6.14	0.01

*TMR: 100 g of a total mixed ration (18% roughage; n=9) and WH: 100 g of beardless wheat hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=7)

Supplemental Table S4. Back-transformed means and SE for models analyzing the effect of eight short-term exposures to 100 g of either TMR* or WH* on behaviours in beef cattle modelled as a rate

Variable	Treatment							
	WH				TMR			
	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit
Bin movements (#/min)	0.22	0.05	0.12	0.33	0.27	0.04	0.18	0.36
Intake (g/min)	1.81	0.21	1.36	2.27	1.78	0.19	1.38	2.17

*TMR: 100 g of a total mixed ration (18% roughage; n=9) and WH: 100 g of beardless wheat hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=7)